

Carbon Quantum Dots Using Polyphenol Compounds: Skin Anti-Aging

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Abstract

Overproduction of collagenase and elastase in response to external factors (e.g. UV exposure, stress, smoking, etc.) can cause matrix breakdown and loss of skin elasticity, eventually leading to wrinkle formation. Recently, there is a lot of attention on prevention of skin aging. Accordingly, the development of anti-aging substances is highly required.

Herein, we investigate the synthesis of novel carbon quantum dots with skin anti-aging effect. The carbon quantum dots using polyphenol compounds as a carbon source are synthesized by microwave-assisted pyrolysis. The resulting novel carbon dots with 3.77 nm in size, highly crystallinity, and unique fluorescence properties show. Anti-aging ability by inhibition the expression of collagenase and elastase. Moreover, their anti-aging properties are analyzed through the level of collagen production in fibroblasts. Therefore, the newly synthesized carbon quantum dots has the potential to be applied as skin- anti-aging ingredient

Synthesis Methods

Carbon quantum dots were synthesized by following the microwave assisted pyrolysis method.

Tannic acid powder was dissolved in distilled water and ethylenediamine.

The solution was heated in a microwave oven (700W) at 2 min.

During this time, the pale orange solution changed to dark-orange by carbonization.

Then cooling to room temperature naturally, the solution was purified by column chromatography using silica gel

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the preparation of carbon quantum dots

Result: Characteristic of Carbon Quantum Dots & Anti-aging properties

Figure 2 TEM image of carbon quantum dots (a), size distribution histogram (b), XRD spectra of carbon quantum dots (c), FTIR spectra of carbon quantum dots (d), UV-Vis absorption and fluorescence spectra of carbon quantum dots (e), fluorescence emission of carbon quantum dots at different excitation wavelength (f).

Figure 3 DPPH free radical scavenging activity (a), collagenase inhibition activity (b), elastase inhibition activity (c), tyrosinase inhibition activity (d), cell viability from MTT assay with different carbon quantum dots concentrations after 24h incubation (e).

Conclusions

In summary, the carbon quantum dots were successfully synthesized by microwave-assisted pyrolysis method with polyphenol compounds as carbon source. The prepared carbon quantum dots exhibited the following characteristics:

1. The maximum DPPH free radical scavenging activity is $88.02 \pm 3.49\%$ at a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$
2. The maximum collagenase inhibition activity is $72.06 \pm 3.49\%$ at a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$
3. The maximum elastase inhibition activity is $39.0 \pm 0.47\%$ at a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$
4. The maximum tyrosinase inhibition activity is $64.8 \pm 7.16\%$ at a concentration of $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$
5. The MTT assays of the new carbon quantum dots show no cytotoxicity up to $100 \mu\text{g/mL}$

These characteristics demonstrated that the new carbon quantum dots has potential to be applied for anti-aging substances.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by Mid-career Researcher Support Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) funded by the Ministry of Science, ICT and Future Planning (NRF-2018R1A2B6006815).